

DEVELOPMENT OF A MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR OPTIMIZATION OF THE OPERATION OF A WIND POWER STATION

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Annotation. The intermittency of wind energy systems and interruptions in energy production require the development of hybrid systems to improve their efficiency. Hybrid systems can be effective in ensuring the continuity of wind energy, enhancing grid stability, and reducing costs. This paper analyzes the interaction of wind energy systems with other energy sources and evaluates energy production efficiency. The operational scenarios of the system are studied using a mathematical model.

Keywords: WGS, Gear-Box, wind flow, Betz power coefficient, DFIG system.

Annotatsiya. Shamol energiyasi tizimlarining intermitentligi va energiya ishlab chiqarishdagi uzilishlar samaradorlikni oshirish uchun gibrid tizimlar yaratishni talab qiladi. Gibrid tizimlar shamol energiyasining uzluksizligini ta'minlash, tarmoq barqarorligini yaxshilash va xarajatlarni kamaytirishda samarali bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu maqola shamol energiyasi tizimlarining boshqa energiya manbalari bilan o'zaro ta'sirini va energiya ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini baholaydi. Tizimning ishlash variantlari matematik model yordamida o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: WGS, Gear-Box, shamol oqimi, Betz quvvat koeffitsienti, DFIG tizimi.

Аннотация. Прерывистость работы систем ветровой энергетики и перебои в производстве энергии требуют разработки гибридных систем для повышения их эффективности. Гибридные системы могут быть эффективными для обеспечения непрерывности ветровой энергии, улучшения стабильности сети и снижения затрат. В данной статье анализируется взаимодействие систем ветровой энергетики с другими источниками энергии и оценивается эффективность производства энергии. Рабочие сценарии системы изучаются с использованием математической модели.

Ключевые слова: WGS, Gear-Box, поток ветра, коэффициент мощности Беца, система DFIG.

Introduction

Uzbekistan is placing significant focus on developing wind energy, considering the global trends that are increasing the demand for renewable energy sources. The country's geographical location and climate provide favorable conditions for efficiently utilizing wind

energy. The Energy Development Plan for 2020-2030 highlights the development of wind energy as one of its key priorities.

The development of wind power plants in Uzbekistan plays a crucial role in ensuring the stability of the energy system, reducing interruptions in energy production, and lowering carbon emissions. It also helps reduce dependence on coal and gas, contributing to economic stability.

To fully realize the potential of wind energy, technological innovations such as advanced inverters and energy storage systems, as well as efficient grid management and energy storage strategies, are essential.

Fig 1 Map series shows electricity generation from renewable energy sources in billion kilowatt-hours

Map shows each country's total electricity generation from all renewable energy sources averaged over the years 2006-2010. Figure 2 illustrates the remarkable evolution of global renewable energy adoption from 2010 to 2020, highlighting the key role that renewable energy has played in changing the energy mix. The growth of renewable energy capacity over the years was 1,240 TWh in 2010, and the capacity has been steadily increasing, reaching 2,960 TWh in 2020. This remarkable growth reflects a global shift towards cleaner and more sustainable energy sources, driven by factors including technological advances, environmental concerns and supportive policies.

Wind Power Generators

The number of wind power systems increased by 25-30% per year between 1994 and 2000. This makes wind power the fastest growing energy source. In 2000, the total wind power production worldwide was 38,000 GWh, and by the end of the year, the total installed capacity was 17,500 MW. The growth is due to the rapid development of new technologies, where new ideas for power generation systems have been implemented, the size of wind farms has increased, the environmental impact has decreased, and the cost per kWh produced has decreased significantly. One of the important drivers of the rapid growth is also the growing concern for the environment. To be able to develop this type of system, it is necessary to combine knowledge from several fields, such as meteorology, aerodynamics, mechanics, electrical engineering and power systems. Wind power generation means producing electricity by converting wind energy into rotational energy in blades and converting that rotational energy into electrical energy in a generator. Wind energy increases with the cube of wind speed, so wind turbines should be installed in areas with higher wind speeds.

Fig 3 Parts of a Wind Turbine

Since electric machines and drives are the main components of wind turbines, it is an urgent need for researchers and engineers to develop advanced electric machines and drives for wind energy. The main characteristics of electric machines and drives, including their advantages and disadvantages, such as torque/power density, efficiency, and cost, are compared and summarized.

Main Part

High-Power Wind-Energy-Conversion Systems

In this section, we will discuss back-to-back connected converters. The architecture will be examined for high-power wind-energy-conversion systems (WECS) in the low-voltage category.

The power converter must have high power density to achieve small footprint and weight. This is an important requirement especially for offshore wind turbines. Low-voltage (LV) converters (690 and 575 V):

Fig 3 Parallel BTB 2L-VSC with common dc-link .

This architecture is for power ratings greater than 0.75 MW in Type 4 turbines (2.5 MW in Type 3 turbines). The current-carrying capability may be increased by connecting the three-phase VSC converters, along with harmonic filters, in parallel.

Wind flow model

The wind speed V at a height h is determined by a logarithmic or power-law profile: Power law (dependence of speed on height):

$$V(h) = V_{ref} \left(\frac{h}{h_{ref}} \right)^\alpha \quad (1)$$

where:

V_{ref} is the wind speed at the height h_{ref} ,

α is the terrain roughness coefficient (usually 0.1–0.4).

Wind turbine power model

The power extracted from the wind is determined by the equation:

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3 C_p \quad (2)$$

where:

ρ is the air density (about 1.225 kg/m³ under normal conditions),

$A = \pi R^2$ is the area covered by the turbine blades (with a rotor radius of R),

V is the wind speed,

C_p is the power factor (maximum 0.593 according to Betz's law, in practice 0.4–0.5).

The impeller slows down the wind speed from v_1 (wind speed at the entrance to the rotor blades) to v_2 (wind speed at the exit from the rotor blades). Assuming constant pressure and therefore constant air density, the air mass flow after and before the turbine is the same

$$v = \frac{(v_1 + v_2)}{2} \quad (3)$$

Mechanical power extracted or extracted from the wind after the wind passes through the turbine

$$P_T = 0.5 * \rho * A * (v_1 + v_2) * (v_1^2 - v_2^2) \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the power coefficient, which is the ratio between P_T and P , is C_p or the rotor coefficient

$$C_p = \frac{P_T}{P} = 0.5 * \left(1 - \frac{v_2^2}{v_1^2}\right) * \left(1 + \frac{v_2}{v_1}\right) \quad (5)$$

This represents a fraction of the wind energy released by the rotor blades. It can be shown when C_p is the maximum value

$$\frac{v_2}{v_1} = \frac{1}{3} \quad (6)$$

this is the ideal wind speed ratio. In this case, the maximum power factor

$$C_p \approx 0.593$$

This is often called the Betz power coefficient, which means that in theory about 60% of the wind energy is captured by the turbine if it reduces the air flow speed to one-third of its original speed. However, practical wind turbines use 0.4 for modern high-speed turbines to 0.5 and has a power factor of 0.2 to 0.4 for low-speed turbines with a large number of blades.

The efficiency of a wind turbine is the ratio of the input power to the ideal net power. A generic model of a wind turbine, available from MATLAB/Simulink, is used in this study in order to assess the operation of a hybrid power plant when the gas turbine is coupled to a wind farm. The wind turbine's performance is governed by pitch angle β , wind speed V_{wind} and wind turbine speed N_{wt} . These are commonly represented in a performance map, as seen in Figure 5.

Fig 5 Performance map of Wind turbine mathematical model

Conclusion

This paper presents a mathematical model of a wind turbine that aims to capture the nonlinear behavior of modern wind turbines. The model is built in MATLAB/Simulink. The system model combines an iterative approach with a constant mass flow rate under steady-state conditions to initialize the state parameters in a dynamic model that uses the intercomponent volume method. The dynamic response of the model was evaluated for a wind farm consisting of 7 wind turbines. The result of this analysis shows the fast transient trajectories that the power system faces due to variable wind speed and fluctuating energy demand. In addition, the behavior of the power system highlighted the need for transient modeling since several operational issues need to be addressed to maintain stability in the grid.

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